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TO EVALUATE THE ORAL MASTICATORY ABILITY AND METABOLIC PARAMETERS OF PATIENTS UNDERGOING UROPLASTY

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ANNOTATION

Congenital cleft lip and palate is one of the most common malformations of the maxillofacial region; in terms of the severity of anatomical and functional disorders, this disease is one of the most severe malformations of the maxillofacial region.

Keywords: congenital cleft lip and palate; children; anomalies of the maxillofacial region.

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ОЦЕНИТЬ ЖЕВАТЕЛЬНУЮ СПОСОБНОСТЬ ПОЛОСТИ РТА И МЕТАБОЛИЧЕСКИЕ ПАРАМЕТРЫ ПАЦИЕНТОВ, ПЕРЕНЕСШИХ УРОПЛАСТИКУ

АННОТАЦИЯ

Врожденная расщелина губы и неба - один из самых распространенных пороков развития челюстно-лицевой области. По тяжести сопутствующих анатомических и функциональных нарушений это заболевание относится к наиболее тяжелым порокам развития.

Ключевые слова: Расщелина губы и неба, присутствующая при рождении; дети; челюстно-лицевые аномалии.

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assistenti
Samarqand davlat tibbiyot universiteti

UROPLASTIKA O'TKAZILGAN BEMORLARNING OG'IZ BO'SHLIG'IDA CHAYNASH QOBILYATI VA METABOLIK PARAMETRLARINI BAHOLASH

ANNOTATSIYA

Tug'ma lab va tanglay yorig'i yuz jag' soxasining eng keng tarqalgan nuqsonlaridan biri, anatomik va funktsional buzilishlarning og'irligi nuqtai nazaridan, bu kasallik maxillofacial soxaning eng og'ir marfofunktsiyalaridan biridir.

Kalit so'zlar: Tug'ilganda mavjud bo'lgan lab va tanglay yorig'i; bolalar; maxillofasiyal anomaliyalar

Introduction: The lack of physician control over changes in masticatory function and oral metabolic parameters at various stages of prosthetic correction in patients represents a significant challenge in modern dentistry. The inability of the majority of practitioners to measure these parameters is associated with a number of factors, including the high cost of complex examinations, insufficient technical support, an underestimation of their necessity, and other problems. The indicators of masticatory function and oral metabolism exert a significant influence on the trajectory and outcome of treatment. Consequently, the inability of most prosthodontists to accurately anticipate changes in these parameters represents a significant challenge. Similarly, the lack of a clear prediction of changes in these parameters represents a significant obstacle for most orthodontists, given its impact on the course and outcome of treatment.

The following section outlines the materials and methods employed in the study. The study was conducted using peripheral blood samples from 100 children with congenital cleft lip and palate, who were undergoing surgical treatment at different stages at the Samarkand, Samarkand, SamSMU, ChLO department. The children were divided into four clinical groups, differing in age ranges and stage of surgical rehabilitation.

Group 1: 20 children aged between 0 and 1 year old (prior to surgical treatment).

Group 2: 30 children aged between 1 and 3 years old (subsequent to cheiloplasty, prior to veloplasty and/or uranoplasty).

Group 3: 30 children aged between 4 and 6 years.

Group 2 comprised 30 children aged between one and three years old, who had undergone cheiloplasty, veloplasty and uranoplasty. Group 3 consisted of 30 children aged between four and six years old. Group 4 comprised 20 children aged between six and 12 years old. The control groups comprised conditionally healthy children of a corresponding age range (20-30 individuals in each group). The concentration of peripheral blood cytokines was determined by enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay (ELISA) on an ASCENT analyser (Finland) using appropriate test systems (CJSC VECTOR-BEST, Rostov-on-Don, Russia). The methodological basis of the dissertation research was based on the consistent use of scientific methods. The work was carried out in accordance with an open comparative prospective study design. The following methods were employed to achieve the set objectives: clinical (anamnesis and objective examination data collection, laboratory analysis and instrumental research results), statistical data analysis methods, and the development of prognostic models.

The results are presented below.

The content of serum cytokines in children of different ages with GVHD at different stages of surgical rehabilitation was assessed. It was found that there was a significant increase in children with a primary lip/palate defect before the stage of cheiloplasty (0-1 year). This is detailed in Table 1. The greatest increase in IFN γ was observed, with the level of IL6 showing the least change. A common feature of all the proinflammatory cytokines studied was a decrease in their content in peripheral blood by the age of 2-3 years after cheiloplasty and before the subsequent stage of surgical rehabilitation, with the concentration of IL6 and IL1 β entering the median control zone. In children belonging to the third and fourth clinical groups with GVHD, a notable decline in IL6 levels was observed, accompanied by a surge in IL1 β and IFN γ concentrations (Table). This suggests that in children with GVHD aged 4-6 years, the osteogenesis disorder accompanied by a pronounced reduction in IL6 is partially compensated for by an increase in IL1 β levels, which serve as a primary driver of osteoclast activity. With regard to the anti-inflammatory cytokine IL4, the observed change in its level in children of different age groups at the stages of surgical rehabilitation was not straightforward. Consequently, the highest level of IL4 was observed in the first clinical group of

children in the first year of life (4 times higher than the age norm) and in children aged 7-12 years old (2.3 times higher than the norm). Conversely, the second and third clinical groups exhibited a twofold decrease in IL4 content (Table). Furthermore, an examination of the IL4 dynamics in the peripheral blood of younger age groups with GERD (groups 1 and 2) reveals the existence of subgroups exhibiting distinct patterns of change in this cytokine. In particular, among children with GVHD in the first year of life, 70% exhibited IL4 levels 3.6 times higher than the age norm, while 30% exceeded it 26 times. In contrast, 80% of children in the second clinical group exhibited IL4 levels 4 times lower than the control, while 20% exhibited levels 3.4 times higher than the age norm. The findings of the study indicated that in children with GERD aged between one and six years, there was an elevation in IL17 levels, which also serves as a stimulator of osteoclastogenesis. This elevation was most pronounced (approximately twofold relative to the age norm) in children within the first year of life. In the second clinical group, there was a 70% increase in IL17 content, while in the third clinical group, there was only a 25% increase. In children aged 7-12 years old with GVHD, there was a more than two-fold decrease. Consequently, the examination of cytokine profiles in children of varying ages with GDM enables us to ascertain that the indications of secondary immune deficiency in this congenital disorder are highly distinctive and are predominantly influenced not only by age-related factors, but also by the type of surgical rehabilitation undertaken at different stages.

Conclusions

In light of the prevalence of somatic diseases and blood parameter abnormalities observed in the preoperative phase, the cohort of children with cleft lip and/or palate was excluded from the study. The incidence of more pronounced postoperative complications in those with a history of exposure to the petrochemical industry provides evidence of impaired reparative regeneration following ureteroplasty. This provides justification for the development and implementation of a post-operative complication prevention method, which will be incorporated into the rehabilitation protocol to enhance the physical and linguistic functions of children following urogenital reconstruction in an industrial region.

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БИМЕДИЦИНА ВА АМАЛИЁТ ЖУРНАЛИ

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